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“LESSONS BY DAY, LULLABIES BY NIGHT”

In the classroom, I teach knowledge and values
I influence and change students' views,
Helping students discover and explore
While unseen burdens sit behind me more.

By night, I cradle my baby close
A motherly love everybody knows
Yet I carry weight that never leaves my part
Postpartum shadows-tired eyes in dark.

In every breastfeeding and pumping session
Silence speaks of untold emotions
Sleepless nights and exhaustion
Sometimes blur the correct vision.

Balancing these two roles is not easy
Labor and effort are necessary.
Who will give hand and light?
To lessons by day, lullabies by night.

Postpartum depression in the teaching vocation
Needs enlightenment and solution,
And every Institution needs to provide
Support and love inside

Let policy and practice intertwine,
To lighten burdens that cross the line.
A shared moral responsibility,
Not just with family but everybody.